

Observation and Study of Landslides Affecting the Tangier: Oued Rmel Motorway Segment

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Abstract : The motorway segment between Tangier and Oued R'mel has experienced, since the beginning of building works, significant instability and landslides linked to a number of geological, hydrogeological and geothermic factors affecting the different formations. The landslides observed are not fully understood, despite many studies conducted on this segment. This study aims at producing new methods to better explain the phenomena behind the landslides, taking into account the geotechnical and geothermic contexts. This analysis builds up on previous studies and geotechnical data collected in the field. The final body of data collected shall be processed through the Plaxis software for a better and customizable view of the landslide problems in the area, which will help to find solutions and stabilize land in the area.

Keywords : landslides, modeling, risk, stabilization

Conference Title : ICCGE 2014 : International Conference on Civil and Geological Engineering

Conference Location : Paris, France

Conference Dates : July 21-22, 2014